

Surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy and machine learning for identification of beta-lactam antibiotics resistance gene fragment in bacterial plasmid

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Combination of SERS and ML techniques showcase a novel biosensing approach for precise identification of beta-lactam antibiotic resistance genes.
- Presents a streamlined method involving enzymatic digestion and selective capture on functionalised SERS substrates, enabling rapid and accurate identification of antibiotic resistance-associated genetic sequences without additional purification steps.
- The robustness of the SERS-ML method is validated through comprehensive control experiments, ensuring its reliability in discerning the presence or absence of the blaTEM gene within bacterial plasmids.
- Demonstrates high sensitivity in detecting concentrations as low as 10⁻⁷ M of the initial plasmid, emphasizing the potential for quick analysis times and high precision.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Antibiotic resistance stands as a critical medical concern, notably evident in commonly prescribed beta-lactam antibiotics. The imperative need for expeditious and precise early detection methods underscores their role in facilitating timely intervention, curbing the propagation of antibiotic resistance, and enhancing patient outcomes.

Results: This study introduces the utilization of surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) in tandem with machine learning (ML) for the sensitive detection of characteristic gene fragments responsible for antibiotic

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Beta-lactam antibiotics resistance
Bacterial plasmid

resistance appearance and spreading. To make the detection procedure close to the real case, we used bacterial plasmids as starting biological objects, containing or not the characteristic gene fragment (up to 1:10 ratio), encoding beta-lactam antibiotics resistance. The plasmids were subjected to enzymatic digestion and without preliminary purification or isolation the created fragments were captured by functional SERS substrates. Based on subsequent SERS measurements, a database was created for the training and validation of ML. Method validation was performed using separately measured spectra, which did not overlap with the database used for ML training. To check the efficiency of recognising the target fragment, control experiments involved bacterial plasmids containing different resistance genes, the use of inappropriate enzymes, or the absence of plasmid.

Significance: SERS-ML allowed express detection of bacterial plasmids containing a characteristic gene fragment up to the 10^{-7} concentration of the initial plasmid, despite the complex composition of the biological sample, including the presence of interfering plasmids. Our approach offers a promising alternative to existing methods for monitoring antibiotic-resistant bacteria, characterized by its simplicity, low detection limit, and the potential for rapid and straightforward analysis.

1. Introduction

Antibiotic resistance poses an ever-growing global health crisis, challenging our ability to combat bacterial infections effectively [1]. The prevalence and dissemination of antibiotic resistance genes in various environments, including clinical settings, food sources, and the environment, have reached alarming levels [2]. To address this pressing concern, it is imperative to develop innovative, highly sensitive and express methods for the analysis of DNA containing antibiotic resistance genes [3]. Such methods should deepen our understanding of the genetic underpinnings of resistance and have far-reaching implications for public health and infection control [4–7] as well as antibiotic development [8] and personalized medicine [9].

In the realm of antibiotic resistance gene analysis, widely used method is polymerase chain reaction, offering high sensitivity and specificity but limited to known targets [10]. An alternative analytical approach, next-generation sequencing, provides comprehensive insights into genomes and metagenomes, capable of detecting both known and novel resistance genes, but is more costly and complex [11]. Another commonly used method, fluorescence in situ hybridization, can visualize gene presence at the cellular level, but is time consuming, requires specialized equipment and expertise [12]. In addition, these commonly used methods are time and professional skills demanding, which can be critical in some urgent cases, where rapid detection of antibiotic resistance is necessary.

As an alternative, the combination of Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) and machine learning (ML) can be considered as synergistic approach for sensitive antibiotic resistance gene detection [13–15]. SERS offers high sensitivity and the ability to detect the presence of targeted compounds up to single molecular limit [16–18]. The use of SERS covers a wide range of potential analytes, from the detection of pesticides or heavy metal ions to the determination of the presence or concentrations of small biorelevant molecules (for example – antibiotics and their metabolites) and the monitoring of small microorganism behaviour (bacteria or mammalian cells) [19–23]. Several works on the use of SERS for determination of the presence of antibiotic resistant bacteria should also be mentioned [24–28]. Most of them, however, operate with model samples compositions and are aimed at the detection of characteristic molecules in a relatively simple matrix.

However, the use of SERS in real clinical practice is constrained by the complexity of samples, where the detection of characteristic signals from targeted biomolecules is often obscured by background signals [29, 30]. In such cases, ML algorithms, proficient in pattern recognition, can be employed to interpret complex SERS spectra, enhancing analysis accuracy by discerning subtle spectral changes associated with presence of specific biomolecules [31–35]. The combination of SERS and ML was successfully employed for the analysis of samples with relatively complicated composition, including the detection of restricted compounds in food, drugs in human liquids, or various contaminants in water or soil, as just a few examples [36–39]. Together, SERS and ML constitute a promising approach for precise and efficient antibiotic

resistance gene detection with possible broad applications in clinical and environmental settings [25,40–42].

In this work, we propose the combination of SERS with ML for the detection of ampicillin resistance gene (blaTEM) presence in bacterial plasmid. The approach includes preparation of SERS substrates that are highly specific to the target DNA sequence, making the resulting spectra easily recognizable with simple ML algorithms like logistic regression. The blaTEM gene plays a crucial role in antibiotic resistance by producing beta-lactamase enzymes that can inactivate beta-lactam antibiotics. Its presence in bacterial plasmids enables the rapid spread of resistance within bacterial populations with associated risks to the health of patients and the safety of medical personnel. Thus, appearance of blaTEM gene should be detected in an express and reliable manner. For these reasons, the utilization of SERS-ML approach (with implementation of portable Raman spectrometer) seems to be a promising alternative.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples preparation and characterization

Materials, reagents, as well as techniques used for samples morphology and chemistry characterization, are described in detail in Supplementary Information. Briefly, plasmon-active Au gratings were prepared by sputtering of 25 nm thick Au layer on periodically patterned polymer substrate. The Au surface was subsequently grafted with carboxylic groups, using the diazonium chemistry approach [43,44]. In the next step NH₂-terminated DNA fragment (further designated as Capture_1) used for subsequent capture of targeted biomolecule (Beta-Lactam antibiotics resistance gene fragment) was covalently linked to SERS-active surface through EDC/sulfo-NHS coupling. Bacterial plasmids were enzymatically digested using suitable endonucleases followed by hybridization with the anchor sequence (i.e. with Capture_1). For Plasmid_1 (pET-31 b (+), 5744 bp) digestion were used high-fidelity endonucleases PvuI-HF and ScaI-HF. The plasmids was incubated at 37 °C for 30 min resulting in cleaved 110 bp blaTEM gene fragment. For Plasmid_2 (c-vector, 4724 bp) were used BamHI-HF and MfeI-HF endonucleases, and the cleaved fragment was 115 bp.

Samples composition and morphology were estimated by Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Ultra-visible spectroscopy (UV-Vis), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS).

SERS spectra were acquired using a 40 × objective with 100 s integration time using portable ProRaman-L Raman spectrometer with 785 nm excitation wavelength. For the collection of SERS spectra, mapping over the surface area of 10 × 10 mm² was performed in the automatic mode (the autofocus function was used). Spectra were recorded at a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹ in the 3000–200 cm⁻¹ wavenumber range. The samples subjected to SERS-ML training and validation include: functionalised grating with ODNs complementary to Plasmid_1 and Plasmid_2 fragment (without addition of any DNA fragment); samples

after “hybridization” with random ssDNA control and after hybridization with target DNA fragment from Plasmid_2; samples with addition of endonucleases *PvuI* and *ScaI* (without Plasmid_1); samples with Plasmid_1 or Plasmid_2 (without endonucleases cleavage); mixes of enzymatically digested Plasmid_1 and Plasmid_2 fragments. Total number of samples was about 150 and from each sample the ca 25 SERS spectra were collected, i.e., total number of spectra used in this work was 3500.

2.2. ML implementation

The main task for machine learning (ML) pipeline was formulated as binary classification task, i. e. distinguishing between samples, containing target plasmid or not (for example – samples containing other plasmids, biomolecules or not containing any of above). Samplewise splitting strategy is presented in Fig. S1. The SERS spectra were divided into two parts in an approximate ratio of 75:25 and used for ML training and validation respectively. In this case, the spectra used for validation were measured on “separately prepared” samples. Such sample splitting strategy was utilized to guarantee that the ML model is evaluated on the spectra of different samples than it was trained on.

Spectra classification was performed with a simple classification pipeline, consisting of principal component analysis (PCA), reducing dimensionality of data to 32 and logistic regression classifier (similar combination was proposed recently [45–47]). After training and evaluating the model, we achieved 99.7 % accuracy, 99.7 % precision, 99.7 % recall. This demonstrates that spectra form two linearly separable clusters and even simple algorithm like logistic regression is sufficient for high-quality classification.

An additional task for ML was to find the so-called regions of importance (i.e., spectral regions important for spectra distinguishing and classification – Fig. S2). The design and evaluation of particular ML algorithms, including the accuracy and precision obtained are described in Supplementary Information (including Figs. S1 and S2).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Main experimental concept

The schematic representation of the proposed approach is presented in Fig. 1. As a functional SERS substrate, we used the periodical Au grating with covalently grafted oligonucleotide(s) (Capture_1). The detailed schema of Capture_1 grafting is presented in Fig. S3. The structure of oligonucleotides was designed to be complementary to specific target gene fragments from bacterial plasmid, containing a characteristic blaTEM gene (detailed description of nucleotides sequences is given in Supplementary Information, Tables 1 and 2). Simultaneously, bacterial plasmids (with or without blaTEM gene) were subjected to restriction enzyme digestion using appropriate endonucleases. This process led to the excision of target fragments associated with antibiotic resistance. In the next step, the SERS substrates were immersed in a buffer solution containing the fragments of cleaved plasmid. The substrates were then heated to 90 °C and gradually cooled to room temperature, facilitating the hybridization between the fragments of blaTEM gene and the surface-bound anchor molecules (Capture_1). To partially eliminate any unhybridized plasmid residues, the samples underwent a thorough triple washing procedure. Subsequently, a database of SERS spectra was collected and subjected to machine learning-based classification, conducted in terms of “YES” or “NO,” corresponding to the presence or absence of the blaTEM gene encoding sequences within the structure of bacterial plasmids.

3.2. SERS substrate characterization

The surface morphology of the used SERS substrate is presented in Fig. 2a (AFM images). As evident, the pristine Au-covered grating exhibits an ordered pattern capable of supporting the excitation and propagation of surface plasmon polariton (SPP) waves. The propagation of SPPs serves to distribute the plasmon-related electric field across the substrate surface, resulting in subsequently measured SERS spectra that are uniform and suitable for machine learning (ML) analysis. The grafting of Au grating surface with Capture_1 did not alter the surface morphology and retained the capacity for SPP excitation. The

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of proposed SERS-ML approach for detection of β -lactam antibiotics resistance gene.

Table 1
Description of control samples used for SERS-ML cross-validation.

Sample name	Sample description	Total number of samples/spectra	Expected/Received SERS-ML answer
Control 1	Functionalised grating with ODN complementary to Plasmid_1 fragment (without addition of any DNA fragment)	5/150	NO/NO
Control 2	Functionalised grating with ODN complementary to Plasmid_2 (control plasmid) fragment (without addition of any DNA fragments in reaction mixture)	5/137	NO/NO
Control 3	Samples after “hybridization” with random ssDNA control	15/425	NO/NO
Control 4	Samples after hybridization with target DNA fragment from Plasmid_2	15/416	NO/NO
Control 5	Without Plasmid_1 (with addition of endonucleases <i>PvuII</i> and <i>ScaI</i>)	15/390	NO/NO
Control 6	Plasmid_1 was added without endonucleases cleavage ()	15/405	NO/NO
Control 7	Plasmid 2 instead of Plasmid 1 before enzymatic cleavage	15/386	NO/NO
Control 8	Capture_2 (control capture) with Plasmid_1 – mismatched ODN combination	15/399	NO/NO
Control_9	Mix of enzymatically digested Plasmid_1 and Plasmid_2 (1:10 ratio).	15/341	YES/YES
Control_10	Mix of enzymatically digested Plasmid_1 and Plasmid_2 (1:100 ratio).	25/612	YES/NO

Table 2
Spectral region of importance (ROI) justified by ML as important for a right decision and its affiliation using a “common” SERS response of DNA molecules (from Refs. [55–57]).

Peak number	Raman shift, cm ⁻¹	Assignment
1	220	Lower-Frequency DNA Vibration
2	340	DNA Bases (A, G)
3	660	DNA Bases (A, C)
4	740	DNA Bases (A, G)
5	850	Sugar-Phosphate Backbone and DNA Bases
6	980	DNA Bases (A, G, C, T)
7	1080	DNA Bases (A, C, T)
8	1220	Sugar-Phosphate Backbone
9	1360	Phosphate Backbone

wavelength position of the SPP absorption band was determined using UV–Vis spectroscopy (Fig. 2b). In the pristine Au grating, a distinct absorption band is observed between 700 and 800 nm. Subsequent grafting of organic moieties led to a slight shift in the position of the SPP band. Considering the width and position of the plasmon absorption band, a common 785 nm laser excitation wavelength was subsequently selected for all SERS measurements. This near infrared excitation wavelength is the biological window, preventing photodegradation of the samples. It also exhibits a low background contribution and high signal to noise ratio compared to other wavelengths [48]. Finally, the successful grafting of organic moieties (-C₆H₄COOH in the first step and Capture_1 in the second) was confirmed using SERS measurements (Fig. 2c). The measurement of the pristine Au grating surface exhibited a featureless spectral pattern. Grafting the Au surface with -C₆H₄COOH (subsequently used for the covalent attachment of Capture_1, as seen in Fig. S3) resulted in the appearance of several SERS bands, with peak assignments detailed in Table S2. These peak positions indicated the presence of benzene rings and carboxylic groups, both consistent with

the chemical structure of the grafted chemical moieties. The grafting of Capture_1 led to a further alteration of the spectral pattern, with the emergence of several additional SERS bands, well correlated with the expected response from oligonucleotide sequences (peak assignments are also given in Table S2). The results of the SERS measurements were consistent with XPS surface chemistry characterization, which indicated a gradual increase in carbon and oxygen surface concentration after each step of surface grafting. Additionally, the XPS analysis revealed the attenuation of characteristic Au signals and the appearance of nitrogen XPS peaks following the grafting of Capture_1 (Fig. S4).

3.3. Cleavage of blaTEM-containing bacterial plasmid and entrapment of characteristic oligonucleotide fragment

Concurrently with the preparation and functionalization of the SERS substrate, we performed the restriction enzyme digestion of the bacterial plasmid (concentration – 0.5 ng/μL). The enzymes were selected to cleave a target oligonucleotide sequence (blaTEM gene fragment) associated with the antibiotic resistance, the structure of the initial plasmid and restricted gene fragment are presented in Supplementary Information). It is worth noting again that Capture_1 was chosen to be compatible with this particular oligonucleotide sequence. Agarose gel electrophoresis was performed to confirm proper cleavage of the plasmid [49]. Obtained results, presented in Fig. 3a, evidenced presence of a DNA fragment of about 100 base pairs, which corresponds to the expected size of the fragment excised from blaTEM encoding gene after *PvuII* and *ScaI* digestion of Plasmid_1. Subsequently, we did not use any sample purification for the detection of targeted plasmid fragments, which significantly simplifies the overall analytical procedure.

In the next step, we carried out the hybridization of the oligonucleotide fragment of blaTEM gene with Capture_1 on the functional SERS-active surface. It is noteworthy that for this purpose, we directly utilized the solution containing the digested plasmid, without prior separation of DNA fragments or its purification from others (bio)molecules. This approach significantly simplifies the experimental procedure and makes it more amenable to rapid analysis. The hybridization was performed using a careful cycle of sample heating and cooling, ensuring partially selective entrapment of the targeted plasmid fragment. During the hybridization of the characteristic blaTEM fragment, the SERS substrate was immersed in the solution, heated to 90 °C, and then slowly cooled down. It is important to note that the previously applied covalent surface grafting method enabled us to utilize these experimental conditions [50]. Traditional thiol chemistry, commonly used for surface modification, may not ensure the survival of grafted chemical moieties at 90 °C [51]. Under heating, the two strands of DNA are pulled apart, resulting in the formation of single-strand DNA. Subsequently, during the gradual cooling process, some of these single-strand fragments can bind with the grafted Capture_1 via complementary hybridization. This hybridization step ensures partial selectivity in the subsequent analysis. However, even in this case, it is challenging to prevent the non-specific surface adsorption of other DNA or single-strand oligonucleotide fragments. In subsequent SERS measurements, these randomly entrapped fragments can generate a spectral background, often complicating the interpretation of SERS spectra and making their analysis more intricate. The surface entrapment of the characteristic blaTEM encoding sequence resulted in subtle changes in the SERS spectra (as is demonstrated in Fig. 3b compared to Fig. 2c, peak assignment is presented in Table S2). Nevertheless, the observed changes in the spectral pattern can not be quite pronounced, since all oligonucleotide sequences have a similar chemical structure with respect to SERS, and produce similar vibration bands. To overcome this challenge, complicated experimental strategies, such as dual amplification process under enzymes catalysis have been previously used [52]. As a simple alternative approach, the subsequent utilization of machine learning algorithms for spectrum interpretation was suggested to recognize the difference between similar oligonucleotide(s) and minimize the effect of non-specific (bio)molecules

Fig. 2. (a) - AFM images of the grating, (b) - UV-Vis spectra in different stages of grating grafting, (c) - SERS spectra.

Fig. 3. (a) - Agarose-gel-electrophoresis analysis of enzymatically digested bacterial plasmid pET-31 b (+). The insert highlights the presence of the expected fragment of blaTEM gene with length of 100 base pair; (b) - SERS spectrum of Au surface after Plasmid_1 fragment hybridization with Capture_1.

adsorption [13,33].

3.4. Preparation of mixed and control samples

Next, we proceeded with the preparation and analysis of control samples, as summarized in Table 1 (sequences of utilized plasmids, used endonucleases and abbreviations are given in Supplementary Information). These control samples included positive and negative controls. In the positive one, the specific oligonucleotide fragment (corresponding to blaTEM gene fragment) was detected against a background of other fragments. The negative controls represent the absence of gene fragment (s) (Control 1, Control 2); presence of random ssDNA (Control 3) or gene fragments formed after enzymatically digestion of Plasmid_2, which did not encode blaTEM gene (Control 4); addition of biomolecules without targeted Plasmid_1 (in particular, endonucleases used for plasmid cleavage – Control 5); non-digested Plasmid_1 (Control 6); Plasmid_2

digested with unsuitable endonucleases (Control 7); utilization of “non-correct” SERS surface grafting (Capture 2 instead of Capture 1, with addition of restricted digested Plasmid_1 – Control 8). Specifically, we utilized an alternative control plasmid that does not encode beta-lactamase but has Kan^r marker gene that provides resistance to kanamycin. This control plasmid underwent endonucleases digestion using either enzymes selected for blaTEM encoded plasmid cleavage (Plasmid_1) or alternative enzymes utilized for the control plasmid diestion – MfeI and BamHI. Additionally, we included samples without the addition of blaTEM plasmid or control plasmid. These measurements aimed to model “real” scenarios, such as the presence of bacterial plasmids that do not encode antibiotic resistance or, even more broadly, the complete absence of plasmid DNA in the analyzed samples. They were performed to verify the capability of the proposed concept to detect the specific oligonucleotide fragment accurately and to ensure that it does not produce “false positive” results.

Lastly, we mixed the blaTEM containing plasmid and control plasmid (ratio – 1:10) and subjected these model samples to enzymatic digestion and subsequent SERS-ML analysis (designated as Control 9 in Table 1). These experiments were designed to simulate closer to reality situation, where bacteria resistant to the target antibiotic may coexist with non-resistant bacteria.

3.5. SERS-ML approach utilization

First, the SERS spectra, measured using pristine plasmids deposited on the plasmon active Au grating surface (i.e., on a simple Au grating without Capture_1) are presented in Fig. S5. As is evident, it is almost impossible to distinguish the difference between plasmids that encode antibiotic resistance or not. In turn, examples of SERS spectra measured on the functional SERS substrate after interaction with enzymatically digested Plasmid_1 and “control” Plasmid_2 are presented in Fig. 4a and b. A few examples of SERS spectra collected after the targeted fragments entrapped are given in Supplementary Information (Fig. S6). Despite the convergence of the relative spectra, it is still impossible to distinguish the presence of characteristic fragments that encode antibiotic resistance. In turn, the absence of characteristic amorphous carbon peaks also indicates the survival of biological molecules during the SERS measurement and the absence of sample degradation. As is evident, the spectral pattern in the case of closed to real samples is significantly distorted (unlike, for example, the model case of relatively short ssDNA grafted to the sample surface Fig. 2c vs. Fig. 4a). This worsening of the SERS signal can be attributed to a partial nonspecific sorption of biomolecules on the SERS substrate, as well as to portable Raman spectrometer, which was used to make detection procedure cheaper and

faster. In particular, the measured spectra patterns appear intricate, with wide overlaps and interfering peaks. While some differences in the spectral patterns can be observed, an operator’s unambiguous interpretation of the spectra is virtually impossible and may lead to errors. To overcome this challenge, we subjected the created spectral database (comprising data from all samples, including those from blaTEM plasmid and control samples listed in Table 1) to ML-based interpretation. Spectra classification was performed with a simple classification pipeline, consisting of principal component analysis (PCA), reducing dimensionality of data to 32 and logistic regression classifier. The details of the employed ML approach are described in the data processing section (in Supplementary Information). By choosing PCA and logistic regression, we demonstrated that even a simpler machine learning technique is sufficient to detect gene fragments while remaining fully interpretable. This highlights the strength of our proposed analytical approach and provides evidence that the spectra of samples containing the gene of interest are clearly distinguishable from those without it. Even in this case the better accuracy and precision was obtained, compare with such alternative algorithms as k-nearest neighbours, linear discriminant analysis and decision tree. It should be noted that the blinking validation of the SERS-ML approach was performed using of separate spectra (measured on separately prepared samples. The SERS spectra arrays measured with “unknown” for MSL samples are presented in Fig. S7). The SERS spectra collected using these samples did not overlap with the initial database used for ML training. Thus, blinking validation really allows one to estimate the efficiency of SERS-ML approach for the detection of a characteristic gene fragment in a situation close to real.

The details of the employed ML approach are described in the data

Fig. 4. (a) - averaged SERS spectra of samples containing plasmid encodes blaTEM gene, (b) - averaged SERS spectra of samples that did not contain target DNA fragment (enzymatically digested control Plasmid_2), (c) - UMAP [53] projection of SERS spectra in 2D space, (d) - regions of importance for classification task (square of logistic regression coefficients).

processing section (in Supplementary Information). The central task for the machine learning model was formulated as follows: detect the presence of the specific fragment of blaTEM gene in the case of the Plasmid_1 or its mixture with the control plasmid (Plasmid_2) (ML will provide answer "YES" in this case) and its absence in all other case (ML will provide the answer "NO") for other samples that did not contain the characteristic oligonucleotide sequence. Furthermore, we introduced the extraction of specific regions-of-importance (ROIs) from the spectra. This allowed us to correlate the results of the ML spectral analysis with the expected SERS signals from the captured oligonucleotide sequence, enhancing the accuracy of our analysis.

The preprocessed spectra were projected to the 2D space with the UMAP algorithm (Fig. 4c, for comparison, the results obtained with PCA utilization are given in Fig. S8). As evident, the use of various samples (from Table 1) led to the creation of several distinct clusters in this projection. Good separation of target DNA containing and not-containing spectra was observed, which proves that even simple ML algorithm should be able to effectively distinguish between "YES" and "NO" classes. Specifically, the characteristic clusters corresponding to the presence of the fragment of blaTEM gene from Plasmid_1 in the sample are well-separated from the others (answer "YES") for both cases - pristine Plasmid_1 utilization (this means that previous plasmid enzymatic digestion, before characteristic fragment capturing, is necessary step) or its previous mix with Plasmid_2. This demonstrates the significance of logistic regression, which provides a correct response with 99.6 % accuracy (for better clarity, the confusion matrices are presented in Fig. S9). Thus, the proposed approach is capable of detecting the presence of the beta-lactam antibiotic resistance gene fragment in the bacterial plasmid in a simple, express and non-demanding way (in terms of equipment used or staff training) [25,54]. Furthermore, this detection can be performed even in the presence of another bacterial plasmid that lacks this gene fragment. Moreover, despite its low initial concentration (100 bp in the 4602 bp plasmid, 0.5 ng/ μ L), we achieved successful detection of the blaTEM gene fragment even in the presence of fragments from a control "background" plasmid. Finally, the presence of the control plasmid, as well as other (random) DNA fragments (Controls 1–8 in Table 1), did not lead to "false positive" responses, demonstrating the reliability of the proposed SERS-ML approach - the corresponding clusters are well separated in 2D space and the "NO" response was obtained with a probability greater than 99.6 %.

We also estimated the mixed samples with a decreased concentration of Plasmid_1 – Control_10. As is evident, the further decrease of the Plasmid_1 portion in the initial mixture (control_10) results in a false-negative detection result. Therefore, the proposed approach is limited by the amount of characteristic plasmids (encoding antibiotic resistance) in the mix with others (not encoding resistance) plasmids.

The additional advantage of the proposed approach is a short detection time. Specifically, the enzymatic digestion of bacteria plasmid takes 30 min. Subsequent capturing of the target fragment on the SERS surface was conducted within 40 min. The measurement of the SERS spectra database with a limited number of spectra (in the general case, 10–30 spectra) takes 20–30 min. Thus, the total analysis time is about 100 min.

Finally, the extracted regions-of-importance (ROIs) are presented in Fig. 4d, and it is evident that their positions correlate with the reported characteristic vibration bands of the oligonucleotide(s) (Table 2). This observation indicates that the primary decision made by ML is indeed based on the spectral features generated by the grafted chemical moieties. Furthermore, the characteristic regions of all nucleobases vibration (A, G, C, T) as well as the phosphate backbones are crucial from the machine learning perspective for the correct interpretation of SERS spectra. This suggests that even small deviations in the overall number of sequences entrapped by Capture_1 from the solution, as well as the relative ratio of entrapped nucleotides, are important parameters for SERS-ML detection of digested bacterial plasmids containing the

blaTEM gene.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we proposed the utilization of a surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy and Machine Learning (SERS-ML) approach for the detection of beta-lactam antibiotics resistance gene in biological samples. We prepared SERS substrates by functionalizing the surface of plasmon-active gold gratings with an oligonucleotide sequence, which is capable of entrapping the specific fragment of blaTEM gene via complementary hybridization. Bacterial plasmids carrying antibiotic resistance genes were enzymatically digested, and the resulting oligonucleotide fragments were immobilized on SERS surface using a heating/cooling cycle without the need for prior sample purification or separation. As control samples, we used a control plasmid that does not encode beta-lactamase gene, random ssDNA sequence and a range of other samples with or without alternative biomolecules presence. In most cases, the measured SERS spectra exhibited complex spectral patterns that could not be reliably interpreted manually due to the risk of interpretation errors. However, the use of the SERS-ML approach allowed us to clearly distinguish between samples containing the specific antibiotic resistance gene fragment and other control samples. It is also important that the verification of the proposed approach was performed using previously "unknown" for SERS-ML samples. The proposed detection approach successfully identified the presence of the target gene fragment even at low plasmid concentrations (0.1 nM). In summary, our approach offers a rapid alternative for detecting antibiotic resistance genes, potentially streamlining the process and enhancing patient care quality and safety. The key advantages include reduced reliance on bacterial culturing and equipment. This approach holds promise for detecting various DNA sequences given the knowledge of complementary sequences. Furthermore, SERS-ML could be directly applied to elucidate bacterial communication (transfer of beta-lactam resistance genes) and prevent the spread of antibiotic resistance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anastasia Skvortsova: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Andrii Trelin:** Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Olga Guselnikova:** Methodology, Data curation. **Alexandra Pershina:** Data curation, Conceptualization. **Barbora Vokata:** Investigation. **Vaclav Svorcik:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Oleksiy Lyutakov:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

X The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data presented in this study are available online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12740804>.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2024.343118>.

References

- [1] S. Yadav, A. Kapley, Antibiotic resistance: global health crisis and metagenomics, *Biotechnol. Rep.* 29 (2021) e00604, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.btre.2021.e00604>.
- [2] A. Savoldi, E. Carrara, D.Y. Graham, M. Conti, E. Tacconelli, Prevalence of antibiotic resistance in *Helicobacter pylori*: a systematic review and meta-analysis in world health organization regions, *Gastroenterology* 155 (2018) 1372–1382. e17, <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.gastro.2018.07.007>.
- [3] R.S. McInnes, G.E. McCallum, L.E. Lamberte, W. van Schaik, Horizontal transfer of antibiotic resistance genes in the human gut microbiome, *Curr. Opin. Microbiol.* 53 (2020) 35–43, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2020.02.002>.
- [4] R. Fang, X. Liu, Z. Zheng, B. Lv, J. Wang, Y. Su, B. Xie, D. Wu, Can antibiotic resistance genes in household food waste be reduced by earthworm vermicomposting? Underpinning mechanisms and strategies, *Rev. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 261 (2023) 1, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44169-023-00025-1>.
- [5] A. Savoldi, E. Carrara, B.P. Gladstone, A.M. Azzini, S. Göpel, E. Tacconelli, Gross national income and antibiotic resistance in invasive isolates: analysis of the top-ranked antibiotic-resistant bacteria on the 2017 WHO priority list, *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.* 74 (2019) 3619–3625, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkz381>.
- [6] L.M. Weiner-Lastinger, S. Abner, J.R. Edwards, A.J. Kallen, M. Karlsson, S. Magill, D. Pollock, I. See, M.M. Soe, M.S. Walters, M.A. Dudeck, Antimicrobial-resistant pathogens associated with adult healthcare-associated infections: summary of data reported to the National Healthcare Safety Network, 2015–2017, *Infect. Control Hosp. Epidemiol.* 41 (2020) 1–18, <https://doi.org/10.1017/ice.2019.296>.
- [7] G. Reichert, S. Hilgert, S. Fuchs, J.C.R. Azevedo, Emerging contaminants and antibiotic resistance in the different environmental matrices of Latin America, *Environ. Pollut.* 255 (2019) 113140, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.113140>.
- [8] C. Årdal, M. Balasegaram, R. Laxminarayan, D. McAdams, K. Outtersson, J.H. Rex, N. Sumpradit, Antibiotic development — economic, regulatory and societal challenges, *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 18 (2020) 267–274, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-019-0293-3>.
- [9] C. Moser, C.J. Lerche, K. Thomsen, T. Hartvig, J. Schierbeck, P.Ø. Jensen, O. Ciofu, N. Høiby, Antibiotic therapy as personalized medicine – general considerations and complicating factors, *APMIS* 127 (2019) 361–371, <https://doi.org/10.1111/apm.12951>.
- [10] M. Frieri, K. Kumar, A. Boutin, Antibiotic resistance, *J. Infect. Public Health* 10 (2017) 369–378, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiph.2016.08.007>.
- [11] A. Bhattacharya, P. Leprohon, S. Bigot, P.K. Padmanabhan, A. Mukherjee, G. Roy, H. Gingras, A. Mestdagh, B. Papadopoulos, M. Ouellette, Coupling chemical mutagenesis to next generation sequencing for the identification of drug resistance mutations in *Leishmania*, *Nat. Commun.* 10 (2019) 5627, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-13344-6>.
- [12] V. Kandavalli, P. Karempudi, J. Larsson, J. Elf, Rapid antibiotic susceptibility testing and species identification for mixed samples, *Nat. Commun.* 13 (2022) 6215, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-33659-1>.
- [13] A. Skvortsova, A. Trelin, P. Kriz, R. Elashnikov, B. Vokata, P. Ulbrich, A. Pershina, V. Svorcik, O. Guselnikova, O. Lyutakov, SERS and advanced chemometrics – utilization of Siamese neural network for picomolar identification of beta-lactam antibiotics resistance gene fragment, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1192 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2021.339373>.
- [14] T. Dai, Z. Xiao, D. Shan, A. Moreno, H. Li, M. Prakash, N. Banaei, J. Rao, Culture-independent multiplexed detection of drug-resistant bacteria using surface-enhanced Raman scattering, *ACS Sens.* 8 (2023) 3264–3271, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.3c01345>.
- [15] C.-Y. Liu, Y.-Y. Han, P.-H. Shih, W.-N. Lian, H.-H. Wang, C.-H. Lin, P.-R. Hsueh, J.-K. Wang, Y.-L. Wang, Rapid bacterial antibiotic susceptibility test based on simple surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopic biomarkers, *Sci. Rep.* 6 (2016) 23375, <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep23375>.
- [16] K. Kneipp, Y. Wang, H. Kneipp, L.T. Perelman, I. Itzkan, R.R. Dasari, M.S. Feld, Single molecule detection using surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS), *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 78 (1997) 1667–1670, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.78.1667>.
- [17] S. Schlücker, Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy: concepts and chemical applications, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 53 (2014) 4756–4795, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201205748>.
- [18] A. Zabelina, A. Trelin, A. Skvortsova, D. Zabelin, V. Burtsev, E. Miliutina, V. Svorcik, O. Lyutakov, Biospired superhydrophobic SERS substrates for machine learning assisted miRNA detection in complex biomatrix below femtomolar limit, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1278 (2023) 341708, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2023.341708>.
- [19] L. Jiang, M.M. Hassan, S. Ali, H. Li, R. Sheng, Q. Chen, Evolving trends in SERS-based techniques for food quality and safety: a review, *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 112 (2021) 225–240, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2021.04.006>.
- [20] J. Wang, J. Wu, Y. Zhang, X. Zhou, Z. Hu, X. Liao, B. Sheng, K. Yuan, X. Wu, H. Cai, H. Zhou, P. Sun, Colorimetric and SERS dual-mode sensing of mercury (II) based on controllable etching of Au@Ag core/shell nanoparticles, *Sensor. Actuator. B Chem.* 330 (2021) 129364, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2020.129364>.
- [21] H. Li, W. Geng, M.M. Hassan, M. Zuo, W. Wei, X. Wu, Q. Ouyang, Q. Chen, Rapid detection of chloramphenicol in food using SERS flexible sensor coupled artificial intelligent tools, *Food Control* 128 (2021) 108186, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2021.108186>.
- [22] M. Muhammad, B. Yan, G. Yao, K. Chao, C. Zhu, Q. Huang, Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy for trace detection of tetracycline and dicyandiamide in milk using transparent substrate of Ag nanoparticle arrays, *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 3 (2020) 7066–7075, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.0c01389>.
- [23] Z. Yu, L. Jiang, R. Liu, W. Zhao, Z. Yang, J. Zhang, S. Jin, Versatile self-assembled MXene-Au nanocomposites for SERS detection of bacteria, antibacterial and photothermal sterilization, *Chem. Eng. J.* 426 (2021) 131914, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.131914>.
- [24] F.U. Ciloglu, A. Mine Saridag, I. Halil Kilic, M. Tokmakci, M. Kahraman, O. Aydin, Identification of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria using surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy and machine learning techniques, *Analyst* 145 (2020) 7559–7570, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0AN00476F>.
- [25] F.U. Ciloglu, A. Caliskan, A.M. Saridag, I.H. Kilic, M. Tokmakci, M. Kahraman, O. Aydin, Drug-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria detection by combining surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) and deep learning techniques, *Sci. Rep.* 11 (2021) 18444, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-97882-4>.
- [26] W.J. Thrift, S. Ronaghi, M. Samad, H. Wei, D.G. Nguyen, A.S. Cabuslay, C. E. Groome, P.J. Santiago, P. Baldi, A.I. Hochbaum, R. Ragan, Deep learning analysis of vibrational spectra of bacterial lysate for rapid antimicrobial susceptibility testing, *ACS Nano* 14 (2020) 15336–15348, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.0c05693>.
- [27] S. Bashir, H. Nawaz, M. Irfan Majeed, M. Mohsin, A. Nawaz, N. Rashid, F. Batool, S. Akbar, M. Abubakar, S. Ahmad, S. Ali, M. Kashif, Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy for the identification of tetracycline-resistant *E. coli* strains, *Spectrochim. Acta. A. Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 258 (2021) 119831, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2021.119831>.
- [28] Z. Al-Shaebi, M. Akdeniz, A.O. Ahmed, M. Altunbek, O. Aydin, Breakthrough Solution for Antimicrobial Resistance Detection: Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy-based on Artificial Intelligence, *Adv. Mater. Interfac.* n/a (n.d.) 2300664, <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202300664>.
- [29] M. Erzina, A. Trelin, O. Guselnikova, A. Skvortsova, K. Strnadova, V. Svorcik, O. Lyutakov, Quantitative detection of α -acid glycoprotein (AGP) level in blood plasma using SERS and CNN transfer learning approach, *Sensor. Actuator. B Chem.* 367 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2022.132057>.
- [30] A. Kozik, M. Pavlova, I. Petrov, V. Bychkov, L. Kim, E. Dorozhko, C. Cheng, R. D. Rodriguez, E. Sheremet, A review of surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy in pathological processes, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1187 (2021) 338978, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2021.338978>.
- [31] R. Beeram, V.S. Vendamani, V.R. Soma, Deep learning approach to overcome signal fluctuations in SERS for efficient On-Site trace explosives detection, *Spectrochim. Acta. A. Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 289 (2023) 122218, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2022.122218>.
- [32] D.P. dos Santos, M.M. Sena, M.R. Almeida, I.O. Mazali, A.C. Olivieri, J.E.L. Villa, Unraveling surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy results through chemometrics and machine learning: principles, progress, and trends, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 415 (2023) 3945–3966, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-023-04620-y>.
- [33] O. Guselnikova, A. Trelin, A. Skvortsova, P. Ulbrich, P. Postnikov, A. Pershina, D. Sykora, V. Svorcik, O. Lyutakov, Label-free surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy with artificial neural network technique for recognition photoinduced DNA damage, *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 145 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2019.111718>.
- [34] J.-F. Masson, J.S. Biggins, E. Ringe, Machine learning for nanoplasmonics, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 18 (2023) 111–123, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-022-01284-0>.
- [35] A. Skvortsova, A. Trelin, A. Sedlar, M. Erzina, M. Travnickova, L. Svobodova, Z. Kolska, J. Siegel, L. Bacakova, V. Svorcik, O. Lyutakov, SERS-CNN approach for non-invasive and non-destructive monitoring of stem cell growth on a universal substrate through an analysis of the cultivation medium, *Sensor. Actuator. B Chem.* 375 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2022.132812>.
- [36] H. Li, M. Mehedi Hassan, J. Wang, W. Wei, M. Zou, Q. Ouyang, Q. Chen, Investigation of nonlinear relationship of surface enhanced Raman scattering signal for robust prediction of thiabendazole in apple, *Food Chem.* 339 (2021) 127843, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.127843>.
- [37] R. Elashnikov, O. Khrystonko, A. Trelin, M. Kuchař, V. Švorčík, O. Lyutakov, Label-free SERS-ML detection of cocaine trace in human blood plasma, *J. Hazard Mater.* 472 (2024) 134525, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2024.134525>.
- [38] R. Beeram, D. Banerjee, L. Murthy Narlagiri, V. Rao Soma, Machine learning for rapid quantification of trace analyte molecules using SERS and flexible plasmonic paper substrates, *Anal. Methods* 14 (2022) 1788–1796, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2AY00408A>.
- [39] Z. Al-Shaebi, F. Uysal Ciloglu, M. Nasser, M. Kahraman, O. Aydin, *Staphylococcus Aureus*-Related antibiotic resistance detection using synergy of Surface-Enhanced Raman spectroscopy and deep learning, *Biomed. Signal Process Control* 91 (2024) 105933, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2023.105933>.
- [40] L. Wang, X.-D. Zhang, J.-W. Tang, Z.-W. Ma, M. Usman, Q.-H. Liu, C.-Y. Wu, F. Li, Z.-B. Zhu, B. Gu, Machine learning analysis of SERS fingerprinting for the rapid determination of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infection and drug resistance, *Comput. Struct. Biotechnol. J.* 20 (2022) 5364–5377, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2022.09.031>.
- [41] S. Das, K. Saxena, J.-C. Tinguely, A. Pal, N.L. Wickramasinghe, A. Khezri, V. Dubey, A. Ahmad, V. Perumal, R. Ahmad, D.N. Wadduwal, B.S. Ahluwalia, D.S. Mehta, SERS nanowire chip and machine learning-enabled classification of wild-type and

- antibiotic-resistant bacteria at species and strain levels, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 15 (2023) 24047–24058, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmi.3c00612>.
- [42] W. Liu, J.-W. Tang, J.-W. Lyu, J.-J. Wang, Y.-C. Pan, X.-Y. Shi, Q.-H. Liu, X. Zhang, B. Gu, L. Wang, Discrimination between carbapenem-resistant and carbapenem-sensitive *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains through computational analysis of surface-enhanced Raman spectra: a pilot study, *Microbiol. Spectr.* 10 (2022) e02409–e02421, <https://doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.02409-21>.
- [43] O. Guselnikova, P. Postnikov, R. Elashnikov, M. Trusova, Y. Kalachyova, M. Libansky, J. Berek, Z. Kolska, V. Švorčík, O. Lyutakov, Surface modification of Au and Ag plasmonic thin films via diazonium chemistry: evaluation of structure and properties, *Colloids Surf. A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 516 (2017) 274–285, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2016.12.040>.
- [44] V.D. Filimonov, M. Trusova, P. Postnikov, E.A. Krasnokutskaya, Y.M. Lee, H. Y. Hwang, H. Kim, K.W. Chi, Unusually stable, versatile, and pure arenediazonium tosylates: their preparation, structures, and synthetic applicability, *Org. Lett.* 10 (2022) 3961–3964, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ol8013528>.
- [45] T. Huang, J. Li, W. Zhang, Application of principal component analysis and logistic regression model in lupus nephritis patients with clinical hypothyroidism, *BMC Med. Res. Methodol.* 20 (2020) 99, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-020-00989-x>.
- [46] E. Kozłowski, D. Mazurkiewicz, J. Sep, T. Zabiński, The use of principal component analysis and logistic regression for cutter state identification, in: J. Machado, F. Soares, J. Trojanowska, V. Ivanov (Eds.), *Innov. Ind. Eng.*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2022, pp. 396–405, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78170-5_34.
- [47] R. Wang, W. Zhang, Y. Li, Y. Jiang, H. Feng, Y. Du, Z. Jiao, L. Lan, X. Liu, B. Li, C. Liu, X. Gu, F. Chu, Y. Shen, C. Zhu, X. Shao, S. Tong, D. Sun, Evaluation of risk factors for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in the middle-aged and elderly rural population of northeast China using logistic regression and principal component analysis, *Risk Manag. Healthc. Pol.* 15 (2022) 1717–1726, <https://doi.org/10.2147/RMHP.S376546>.
- [48] L.T. Kerr, H.J. Byrne, B.M. Hennelly, Optimal choice of sample substrate and laser wavelength for Raman spectroscopic analysis of biological specimen, *Anal. Methods* 7 (2015) 5041–5052, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5AY00327J>.
- [49] G.K. McMaster, G.G. Carmichael, Analysis of single- and double-stranded nucleic acids on polyacrylamide and agarose gels by using glyoxal and acridine orange, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 74 (1977) 4835–4838, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.74.11.4835>.
- [50] L. Laurentius, S.R. Stoyanov, S. Gusarov, A. Kovalenko, R. Du, G.P. Lopinski, M. T. McDermott, Diazonium-derived aryl films on gold nanoparticles: evidence for a carbon–gold covalent bond, *ACS Nano* 5 (2011) 4219–4227, <https://doi.org/10.1021/nn201110r>.
- [51] D.M. Shewchuk, M.T. McDermott, Comparison of diazonium salt derived and thiol derived nitrobenzene layers on gold, *Langmuir* 25 (2009) 4556–4563, <https://doi.org/10.1021/la8040083>.
- [52] Q. Wang, C. Jiang, Y. Zhang, M. Li, X. Shi, Y. Zhang, F. Tian, F. Li, L. Ren, S. Zhang, X. Song, SERS sensor combined with the dual DNA cycling amplification assay for the sensitive detection of antibiotic resistance gene in environmental samples, *Sensor. Actuator. B Chem.* 396 (2023) 134599, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2023.134599>.
- [53] L. McInnes, J. Healy, J. Melville, UMAP: uniform manifold approximation and projection for dimension reduction, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1802.03426>, 2020.
- [54] T. Yu, Y. Fu, J. He, J. Zhang, Y. Xianyu, Identification of antibiotic resistance in ESKAPE pathogens through plasmonic nanosensors and machine learning, *ACS Nano* 17 (2023) 4551–4563, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.2c10584>.
- [55] L.Q. Dong, J.Z. Zhou, L.L. Wu, P. Dong, Z.H. Lin, SERS studies of self-assembled DNA monolayer – characterization of adsorption orientation of oligonucleotide probes and their hybridized helices on gold substrate, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 354 (2002) 458–465, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614\(02\)00163-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614(02)00163-X).
- [56] C. Otto, T.J.J. van den Tweel, F.F.M. de Mul, J. Greve, Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy of DNA bases, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 17 (1986) 289–298, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrs.1250170311>.
- [57] V. Shvalya, A. Vasudevan, M. Modic, M. Abutoama, C. Skubic, N. Nadžar, J. Zavašnik, D. Vengust, A. Zidanšek, I. Abdulhalim, D. Rozman, U. Cvelbar, Bacterial DNA recognition by SERS active plasma-coupled nanogold, *Nano Lett.* 22 (2022) 9757–9765, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.2c02835>.